

Origin, extinction, and ancient DNA of a new fossil insular viper: molecular clues of overseas immigration

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ABSTRACT

Viperinae is a subfamily of viperid snakes whose fossil record in Mediterranean islands is restricted to 12 palaeontological deposits on seven islands, so far. Revision of the material excavated 30 years ago from the Middle/Late Pleistocene–Holocene deposit of Es Pouàs [Eivissa (=Ibiza), Balearic Islands, western Mediterranean] revealed about 6,000 bones of a small-sized viper across different stratigraphic levels. Its morphological characteristics are different enough to known species of *Vipera* to warrant the description of a new species, but the nearly complete mitochondrial genome obtained from this snake based on a sample dated to 16,130±45 BP, suggested it belonged to a new insular population of Lataste's viper (*Vipera latastei*), *Vipera latastei ebusitana* **subsp. nov.** Phylogenetic analysis indicates that the dispersal of the ancestors of *V. l. ebusitana* to Eivissa, most probably from a North-East Iberian population, occurred via overwater colonization < 1.5 Mya, well after the Messinian Salinity Crisis (5.97–5.32 Mya) when land bridges allowed terrestrial colonization of the Balearic Islands by mainland faunas. The morphological differences between *V. l. ebusitana* and the Iberian populations suggest that it is a new dwarf taxon resulting from insular evolutionary processes, becoming extinct shortly after the first human arrival to this island about 4,000 years ago.

KEYWORDS: Serpentes – New taxa – Island fauna – Mitochondrial DNA – Quaternary – Mediterranean – Molecular clocks

INTRODUCTION

Viperinae Oppel, 1811 (the true vipers) is a subfamily of viperid snakes currently distributed throughout Asia, Africa, and Europe, and comprising up to 102 extant species and 13 genera (Phelps, 2010), although the taxonomic status of some species/subspecies remains under discussion (Freitas *et al.*, 2020). The fossil record of viperines in Europe is extensive and begins in the Early Miocene, about 23.8–22.8 Myr (Szyndlar & Rage, 2002). However, true vipers are scarce in the fossil record of the Mediterranean islands, known from only 12 paleontological sites on seven islands (Table 1). Further, these specimens are mainly isolated vertebrae, which often defy precise taxonomic assignment. Consequently, the diversity and evolutionary history of Mediterranean vipers are poorly understood and extensively debated. Of particular interest is the identification of self-introduced endemic viper lineages versus those that have potentially been translocated by humans, as this is critical for understanding the assembly of the Mediterranean islands reptile fauna and the origins of fossil taxa.

The Cyclades viper [*Macrovipera lebetina schweizeri* or *M. schweizeri* (Werner, 1935), depending on authors] is often considered the only extant endemic Mediterranean island viperine taxon (Nilson & Andrén, 1988; Stümpel & Joger, 2009), though its presence on the Turkish mainland suggests its Mediterranean distribution may in fact derive from recent anthropic introduction (Stümpel & Joger, 2009; Freitas *et al.*, 2020). Likewise, it is debated whether *Montivipera xanthina* (Gray, 1849) on some Aegean islands (Kurnaz *et al.*, 2018) and *Vipera aspis* (Linnaeus, 1758) on Elba (Masseti & Zuffi, 2011) represent populations introduced by humans or founded by natural autonomous dispersal, whereas the presence of the latter species in Montecristo island has been interpreted as a human mediated colonization (Barbanera *et al.*, 2009). The earliest known presence of *M. lebetina lebetina* (Linnaeus, 1758) on Cyprus dates to the 9th millennium BC (Bailon, 1999), probably as the result of human introduction, though its allochthonous character is still under discussion. In contrast, a recently extirpated population of *Vipera latastei* Boscá, 1878 on the Columbretes

Islands likely originated as the result of natural dispersal (Marquina *et al.*, 2014; Ruiz Sánchez *et al.*, 2019), as did the populations of *V. aspis* on Sicily (Barbanera *et al.*, 2009; Martínez-Freiría *et al.*, 2020) and *Vipera ammodytes* (Linnaeus, 1758) on the Cyclades (Ursenbacher *et al.*, 2008).

The capacity for members of *Vipera* Laurenti, 1768 in particular to autonomously colonise Mediterranean islands is also supported by the Balearic Islands fossil record, from which a number of putative *Vipera* taxa have been described. The Balearic Islands (western Mediterranean Sea) are the most isolated islands in the Mediterranean and are composed of two groups (Fig. 1): the western Pityusic Islands (Eivissa, Formentera, and surrounding islets) and the eastern Gymnesic Islands (Mallorca, Menorca, and surrounding islets). Both groups have remained isolated from mainland and from one another since the end of the Messinian, 5.33 Mya (Palmer *et al.*, 1999; Bover *et al.*, 2008). The Balearic fossil record of snakes is currently restricted to the Pliocene/Early Pleistocene of the Gymnesics, with the apparent absence of snakes from the Pityusic archipelago an accepted zoological peculiarity (e.g., Boscá, 1883; Compte Sart, 1966; Hinckley *et al.*, 2017). In Menorca *Vipera natiensis* Bailon, García-Porta & Quintana-Cardona, 2002 and *Vipera* sp. were described from Pliocene deposits and an indeterminate viperid from a Middle Miocene site (Bailon *et al.*, 2002). In Mallorca, the Pliocene site of Caló den Rafelino yielded two vertebrae of a large viperid attributed to the ‘Oriental Vipers Complex’ (OVC) (Bailon *et al.*, 2010), and other small vertebrae attributed to cf. *V. natiensis* (Bover *et al.*, 2014), while the Early Pliocene (Zanclean) deposit of Na Burguesa-1 yielded remains of another ‘OVC’ viper (Bover *et al.*, 2014; Torres *et al.*, 2014). While it is likely impossible to use DNA to establish the relationships between Pliocene taxa and extant species, Pleistocene and Holocene subfossil faunal remains from the Balearic islands are amenable to ancient DNA analysis (Lalueza-Fox *et al.*, 2000, 2002, 2005a,b; Ramírez *et al.*, 2009; Bover *et al.*, 2018, 2019, 2020).

Ancient DNA studies have been mainly focused on mammalian taxa, especially

humans. In contrast, analyses of ancient genetic data from fossil or subfossil reptiles are scarce (but see Austin & Arnold, 2001, 2006; Austin *et al.*, 2003, 2004; Arnold & Bour, 2008; Sommer *et al.*, 2009; Parham *et al.*, 2004; Kehlmaier *et al.*, 2017, 2020; Seersholm *et al.*, 2018; Mahony *et al.*, 2020). Ancient DNA from snake taxa in particular has apparently only been obtained from ethanol or formalin-fixed museum specimens (Ruane & Austin, 2017; Allentoft *et al.*, 2018). In this study we report the presence of fossil viper remains from the Late Pleistocene–Holocene levels of Es Pouàs (Santa Agnès de Corona) and the Early Pleistocene site of Cova de ca na Reia (Santa Eulària des Riu) on the island of Eivissa (Fig. 1). In addition, we present ancient mitochondrial genetic data from the Es Pouàs viper, which allowed us to accurately establish its taxonomic identity and identify its mainland source region, revealing the first recorded overwater colonization of the Balearic Islands by a terrestrial vertebrate postdating the Messinian Salinity Crisis (MSC, Upper Miocene).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

MATERIAL

So far, Es Pouàs (Sant Antoni de Portmany, Eivissa) is the most important vertebrate palaeontological site of the Pityusic Islands with a Middle/Late Pleistocene to Holocene chronology. The absence of terrestrial mammals in the fossiliferous record of this cave suggests that the Pityusics were the sole islands over the entire Mediterranean region without terrestrial mammals (e.g., Florit *et al.*, 1989; Alcover *et al.*, 1994; Seguí & Alcover, 1999; McMinn *et al.*, 2005; Guerra, 2015), with the vertebrate fauna apparently only comprising birds, bats, and a lizard until the first human arrival about four millennia ago (e.g., Alcover *et al.*, 1981; Alcover, 2008). However, a recent revision of the material excavated from Es Pouàs between 1989 and 1994 revealed ca. 6,000 bones of a small viper in different stratigraphic levels of the grid-squares A2, A3, A4 and A5 [see Alcover & Muntaner (1986), and Guerra (2015) for the topographical survey and reference grid of the site] (Table 2). The uppermost

prehuman paleontological level yielded a radiocarbon age of 6130 ± 80 BP ($5295\text{--}4848$ 2σ cal BC; UtC-6222, obtained on *Rallus eivissensis* McMinn, Palmer & Alcover, 2005 bone collagen; grid-square A3 at -60/-80 cm depth), while the lowermost dated level of this grid-square furnished a radiocarbon age of $30,700 \pm 600$ ($34,694\text{--}32,523$ 2σ cal BC UtC-2929, on bird bone collagen; A3, level 8). The viper bones used for our study's morphological analysis were obtained from grid-squares A3 (from -60/-80 cm to level 8) and A2 (from -70/-90 cm to -350/-370 cm) whereas vertebrae used in our study's molecular analyses came from grid-square A2 (-110/-130 cm). A combined sample of 64 viper vertebrae from this same grid and level (IMEDEA 106583; total weight: 0.53 g) were radiocarbon dated at $16,130 \pm 45$ BP ($17,620\text{--}17,320$ 2σ cal BC; RICH-24981). In addition, a single ophidian caudal vertebra was obtained from Cova de ca na Reia (Santa Eulària del Riu, Eivissa), a palaeontological site assumed to belong to Gelasian/Calabrian (Alcover & Agustí, 1985).

All specimens studied here are curated at the vertebrate collection of the Institut Mediterrani d'Estudis Avançats (Esporles, Spain) (acronym: IMEDEA), while a small sample of 12 unnumbered vertebrae has been deposited at the Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle (Paris). The comparative material of several species of *Vipera* used in this study came from the IMEDEA and Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle (Paris, France) (acronym: MNHN) collections [*V. ammodytes* (MNHN-ZA-AC 2020-2), *V. aspis* (IMEDEA106926 and MNHN 1967-100), *V. latastei* (IMEDEA 106925 and MNHN-ZA-AC 2020-1), *V. monticola* Saint-Girons, 1954 (RA-MNHN 1961-0334), *V. seoanei* Lataste, 1879 (IMEDEA106927 and MNHN-ZA-AC 2020-3). and *V. ursinii* (Bonaparte, 1835) (MNHN-ZA-AC 1967-277)].

Scanning electron microscope (HITACHI S-3400N) photographs of the specimens were taken at the Scientific and Technical Services of the Universitat de les Illes Balears (Mallorca). The measurements (in mm) of the vertebrae were taken using a Digital Microscope AM7915MZT Dino-Lite Edge. The measurements and nomenclature used in the morphological description of the specimens follow Szyndlar (1984).

BODY SIZE ESTIMATION

Several vertebral measurements and methods – including regression and Maximum Likelihood – have been used to estimate body length in snakes (e.g., Head *et al.*, 2009; LaDuke *et al.*, 2010; McCartney *et al.*, 2018), but it is usually required a precise identification of the position of the vertebra in the column, which in the case of isolated vertebrae can be a difficult task. The discussion on this topic is beyond the purpose of this paper, and an approximate body length estimate would be informative enough to understand body size differences between extant *Vipera* and the fossil snake presented here. For this reason, we followed Bailon *et al.* (2002) to estimate body length of the extinct viper from Eivissa using linear regression of the vertebral measurement CL (Centrum length) in intermediate trunk vertebrae, which showed a high coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.9512$) (see Table S1). The complete ossification degree of some structures of these vertebrae, especially the thick walls and condyle-cotyle/neural arch ratio, indicated that the material used to estimate the body size was from adult specimens. We estimated Total Body Length (TBL) using the equation $Y = 1.2523X + 4.6234$ obtained from data of nine individuals belonging to six different species of *Vipera*, where e^Y = total length of the viper and $X = \ln$ of the vertebrae centrum length (CL).

ANCIENT DNA EXTRACTION AND LIBRARY CONSTRUCTION

All extraction and library construction steps were performed in the ancient DNA laboratory of the Australian Centre for Ancient DNA (ACAD) at the University of Adelaide (Australia). Fifteen vertebrae of the fossil snake from Es Pouàs [grid A2, -110/-130 cm, radiocarbon age $16,130 \pm 45$ BP ($17,620$ – $17,320$ 2σ cal BC; RICH-24981, McMinn *et al.*, 2005)] were washed three times in 1.5 mL of water, with a final wash using 1.5 mL of absolute ethanol, air dried, and UV irradiated for 15 min on each side. Vertebrae were

pulverized using a hammer, and the 110 mg remaining were digested on a rotary wheel for 1 hr in 1 mL of 0.5 M EDTA (pH 8.0) (Life Technologies, Carlsbad, CA, USA). EDTA was removed by pipetting and bone powder was then digested at 55°C under constant rotation for 24 hrs in a digestion buffer consisting of 970 mL 0.5 M EDTA and 30 µl Proteinase-K 20 mg/mL (Life Technologies). Supernatant was collected following centrifugation and DNA was bound to suspended silicon dioxide particles (Brotherton *et al.*, 2013) in a modified PB binding buffer [13.6 mL PB buffer (Qiagen, Valencia, CA, USA), 420 µl 3 M sodium acetate (~pH 5) (Sigma-Aldrich, Saint Louis, MO, USA), and 7 µl Tween-20 (Sigma-Aldrich)]. After purification with 80% ethanol, the sample was eluted in 100 µl of TLE (10 mM Tris, 0.1 mM EDTA pH 8.0). A negative control was extracted alongside the samples.

A non-repaired double-stranded DNA library was constructed from this sample following a protocol based on Meyer & Kircher (2010) with modifications used by Llamas *et al.* (2016), which comprised a 7-mer barcode sequence in both truncated P5 and P7 adapters, the use of Platinum Taq Hifi (Invitrogen, Carlsbad, CA, USA) for the first post-Bst PCR library amplification, and the use of Amplitaq Gold (Life Technologies) for subsequent amplifications. The final library was sequenced on an Illumina NextSeq using a 150-cycle Mid Output kit (in PE 2×75 mode).

READ FILTERING, MAPPING AND CONSENSUS GENERATION

The quality of a total of 24,791,817 resulting raw sequencing reads was analysed using fastQC v0.11.2 (<http://www.bioinformatics.babraham.ac.uk/projects/fastqc>). We demultiplexed sequences from the snake sample by filtering both P5 and P7 barcodes (allowing one mismatch) using Sabre v.1.0 (<http://github.com/najoshi/sabre>). Adapter sequences were trimmed with AdapterRemoval v.2.1.7 (Schubert *et al.*, 2016) using the following parameter values: mismatch rate 0.1, minimum Phred quality 4, quality base 33, trim ambiguous bases (N), and trim bases with qualities equal to or less than the given

minimum quality. AdapterRemoval collapsed (merged) paired reads overlapping by at least 11 bp. After trimming, reads shorter than 25 bp were excluded from further analysis. We retained 23,122,029 collapsed reads (~93% of total read pairs) for downstream analysis.

We constructed a draft mitochondrial genome of the snake from Eivissa using a seven step process (see schematic diagram in Fig. S1): 1) Iterative mapping to two published reference genomes (“Multi-reference Iterative Mapping Approach”, MIMA) using BWA (Li & Durbin, 2009); 2) extension of the MIMA reference using MITObim (Hahn *et al.*, 2013); 3) iterative mapping to the MITObim consensus sequence; 4) BLASTn (Altschul *et al.*, 1990) authentication of mapped regions; 5) merging consensus sequences from steps 1 and 3; 6) iterative mapping to merged reference from step 5 and creation of final consensus sequence; and 7) BLASTn and mapDamage (Jónsson *et al.*, 2013) authentication of final consensus sequence. These steps are described in detail below:

1) In step one, we used a Multi-reference Iterative Mapping Approach (MIMA), which involves sequential rounds of mapping, in between which the reference sequence is updated with information from the previous round. Preliminary morphological analysis suggested the ascription of the remains to the genus *Vipera*, based on the well developed hypoapophysis, inclined post- and pre-zygapophysis, and the shape of pterygoid and compound bones (see detailed description below). For this reason, we chose two mitochondrial genome references: *Vipera berus* (Linnaeus, 1758) (GenBank accession number NC_036956) and *Daboia siamensis* (Smith, 1917) [GenBank accession number NC_011391; Garrigues *et al.*, 2005; Wüster *et al.*, 2008; Freitas *et al.*, 2020; mislabelled as *D. russellii* (Shaw & Nodder, 1797) in GenBank according to Freitas *et al.*, 2020]. For each reference, collapsed reads were mapped using BWA v.0.7.17 backtrack algorithm (Li & Durbin, 2009; aln -n 0.001, -o 2, -l 1024). Subsequently, reads with mapping quality lower than Phred 25 were removed using SAMtools v.1.8 (Li *et al.*, 2009) and duplicate reads were filtered using FilterUniqueSAMCons.py (Kircher, 2012). Intermediate 75% majority consensus sequences

were generated using Geneious v.11.1.4 (Biomatters, <http://www.geneious.com>, Kears e *et al.*, 2012), retaining the reference nucleotide for sites with read-depth $< 3\times$. This new consensus was used as the new reference and the process was iterated until no more reads were mapped. Final 75% majority consensus sequences for the iterative mapping against each reference were then generated in Geneious, calling nucleotides only at sites with read-depth $\geq 3\times$. After 16 iterations 2,785 unique reads mapped to the *V. berus* mitogenome (reference coverage = 76%; mean depth = $9\times$), whereas after 13 iterations 1,080 unique reads mapped to the *D. siamensis* mitogenome (reference coverage = 33% coverage; mean depth = $3.2\times$). The consensus sequences generated from iterative mapping against the two different references were identical for regions where they overlapped. We aligned these consensus sequences with the *V. berus* mitogenome using the MUSCLE algorithm implemented in Geneious, and created a new merged reference by retaining nucleotides called from our sequence data and filling any gaps with the corresponding nucleotides from *V. berus*. The merged reference was then used for 6 rounds of iterative mapping (as described above) after which 2,918 unique reads were retained (reference coverage = 78.2%; mean depth = $9.4\times$). We then generated a 75% majority consensus, retaining the reference nucleotide (*V. berus*) in positions with coverage depth $< 3\times$.

2) In step two, we used the MITObim pipeline v.1.8 (Hahn *et al.*, 2013) with default parameters to map all collapsed reads to the consensus generated at the end of step one (see above). MITObim maps all reads to a reference seed using MIRA (Chevreux *et al.*, 1999) and then iteratively attempts to extend mapped contigs. After 11 iterations of mapping, we converted the MAF formatted output file to SAM file format using ‘miraconvert’ in MIRA, then removed duplicate reads using FilterUniqueSAMCons.py, before remapping the 2,966 retained reads using the Geneious read mapper (maximum mismatches per read = 10%; minimum mapping quality = Phred30; maximum gaps per read = 10% read length; maximum gap length = 10bp; minimum overlap = 25bp; word size = 12). We then generated a 75%

majority-rule consensus sequence, retaining the reference nucleotide for sites with coverage depth $< 3\times$.

3) In step three, we used the consensus sequence from step two as the reference for another round of iterative mapping using BWA (as described in step one). After three iterative rounds of mapping we retained 3,261 unique reads (reference coverage = 85.3%; mean depth = $10.6\times$). We then generated a 75% majority-rule consensus sequence, calling nucleotides only for sites with coverage depth $\geq 3\times$.

4) All overlapping fragments in the consensus sequences from steps one and three were identical. However, some fragments were represented in consensus of step three but not in the other consensus (from step one). We analyzed these new fragments using BLASTn in order to verify the authenticity of the sequences. Fifteen fragments were analyzed and all of them matched most closely to species of the genus *Vipera* (generally with Query Cover $> 93\%$ and Identity $> 85\%$).

5) We combined the information from the consensus sequences from steps one and three to create a new merged reference, retaining the *Vipera berus* mitogenome nucleotide only where there was no coverage from our previously mapped reads.

6) In step six, we used the consensus sequence from step five as the reference for a final round of iterative mapping. After two iterations we retained 3,339 unique reads mapped (reference coverage = 86.3%; average depth = $10.8\times$) and generated a final consensus, as described above (i.e., 75% majority threshold, nucleotides called only where coverage depth was $\geq 3\times$).

7) We analysed the final consensus sequence from step six, including degenerate nucleotides, using BLASTn. The top hit was *Vipera berus* (Query Cover = 76%; Identity = 92.7%). Misincorporation and DNA fragmentation patterns in unique mapped reads were assessed using mapDamage v.2.0.8 (Jónsson *et al.*, 2013) (Fig. S2), which displays the expected damage pattern observed in ancient samples (e.g., Briggs *et al.*, 2007).

Consequently, we used this consensus sequence for all downstream analyses.

PHYLOGENETIC AND HAPLOGROUP NETWORK ANALYSES

Following previously published phylogenetic analyses (e.g., Wüster *et al.*, 2008; Freitas *et al.*, 2020), we selected genetic data from the Viperinae genera *Vipera*, *Montivipera* Nilson, Tuniyev, Andren, Orlov, Joger & Hermann, 1999, *Macrovipera* Reuss, 1927, and *Daboia* Gray, 1842 available in GenBank to construct two alignments (Appendices S1 and S2) for Maximum Likelihood (ML) and Bayesian Inference (BI) phylogenetic analyses:

Dataset 1. We downloaded previously published *12S_rRNA*, *16S_rRNA*, *COXI*, *CYTB*, *ND2*, and *ND4* sequences (see Table S2) and aligned them to our Eivissan viper data using the MUSCLE algorithm as implemented in Geneious. Whenever possible, we selected isolated gene sequences from the same individual, or at least from the same geographic region for the same species, resulting in an alignment with 34 samples, comprising a single representative per species.

Dataset 2. As the preliminary results using Dataset 1 (see Fig. S3) indicated that the snake from Eivissa was within the clade comprising *Vipera latastei/monticola*, we substituted the *V. latastei* and *V. monticola* sequences used in Dataset 1 with six sequences representing different populations of *V. latastei* from the Iberian Peninsula and a *V. latastei/monticola* from Morocco (see Table S2), increasing the dataset to 39 samples.

We divided our alignments into *12S_rRNA*, *16S_rRNA*, as well as first, second, and third codon positions of protein coding genes (PCG). Ambiguous regions of rRNAs were removed using stringent default parameters in Gblocks (Castresana, 2000), which kept 213 out of 365 bp (58%) of *12S_rRNA* and 327 out of 425 bp (76%) of *16S_rRNA*. Consequently, the final alignment was 4,164 bp in length (213bp *12S_rRNA*, 327bp *16S_rRNA*, 840bp *COXI*, 1104bp *CYTB*, 1002bp *ND2*, and 678bp *ND4*). We then determined the best partitioning scheme and substitution models for each dataset using PartitionFinder v.2.1.1

(Lanfear *et al.*, 2016; see Table S3). We performed a partitioned Maximum Likelihood analysis in RAxML v.8.2.11 (Stamatakis, 2014), with node support values estimated by performing 1,000 bootstrap replicates. We also performed a partitioned MrBayes v.3.2.3 analysis (Ronquist *et al.*, 2012), comprising four separate runs of four Markov chains each using default priors. Each chain ran for 10^7 generations sampling trees and parameter values every 10^4 generations. Topological convergence was assessed using the average standard deviation of clade (split) frequencies (< 0.02), while convergence in individual parameter values was assessed through broadly overlapping distributions and effective sample sizes > 200 in Tracer v.1.6. All sampled trees were summarised as a majority-rule consensus tree after discarding the first 10% of trees as burn-in.

A partitioned molecular dating analysis was performed on both Datasets using BEAST v.1.8.4 (Drummond *et al.*, 2012), with a Birth-Death tree prior and a single lognormal relaxed clock. The calibration of phylogenetic trees for Viperidae Opperl, 1811 using fossil records is controversial given the lack of remains for some groups and/or regions as well as the ambiguity of associating fossil remains to living taxa (see Stümpel *et al.*, 2016; Martínez-Freiría *et al.*, 2017; Freitas *et al.*, 2020). Most authors recognise these difficulties and generally use a combination of fossil remains, palaeogeography, and/or secondary calibration points to date viperid phylogenetic trees (e.g., Wüster *et al.*, 2008; Ferchaud *et al.*, 2012; Velo-Antón *et al.*, 2012; Zinenko *et al.*, 2015; Alencar *et al.*, 2016; Stümpel *et al.*, 2016; Zheng & Wiens, 2016; Martínez-Freiría *et al.*, 2017; Šmid & Tolley, 2019). Our molecular dating strategy relies on constraining the age of the root of the tree – i.e., the split between *Vipera-Daboia* and *Macrovipera-Montivipera* – in accordance with the results of Zheng & Wiens (2016). Thus, we constrained the age of the root node using a lognormal prior with a mean of 25.5 Mya and standard deviation of 0.1 (for a similar dating approach see Freitas *et al.*, 2020; Martínez-Freiría *et al.*, 2020). Four analyses were run for 10^7 generations sampling every 10^4 generations, discarding the first 10% of samples as burn-in. Convergence was

assessed through combined analysis of four independent runs which parameters showed effective sample sizes > 200 as calculated using Tracer v.1.6 (<http://tree.bio.ed.ac.uk/software/tracer/>). Individual run outputs were combined using LogCombiner v.1.8.4 and a final maximum clade credibility tree was generated using TreeAnnotator v.1.8.4 (Rambaut & Drummond, 2010).

To evaluate the position of the snake from Eivissa within the diversity of *Vipera latastei/monticola*, we aligned the *CYTB* (270 bp) and *ND4* (602 bp) sequences available for *V. latastei/monticola* from Velo-Antón *et al.* (2012), Martínez-Freiría *et al.* (2015, 2020), and Freitas *et al.* (2018) (see Table S4), including the corresponding sequences for the snake from Eivissa, and *Vipera aspis* as outgroup (*CYTB* accession number JX649673, and *ND4* accession number JX649606). The alignment of 872 bp (Appendix S3) with and without outgroup was analysed using RAxML, and the resulting tree without outgroup was used to generate a haplogroup network using Fitch algorithm in Fitchi (Matschiner, 2015) (Figs. 2 and S4). The same dataset was used to graphically depict the pairwise distances between different *V. latastei/monticola* sequences using the heatmap similarity (%) implemented in Geneious.

RESULTS

PHYLOGENETIC ANALYSES

The partial mitochondrial genome sequence for the *Vipera* from Eivissa has a total length of 16,381 bp (GenBank Accession Number MT527189). Up to 3,248 nucleotides are degenerate (3,181 N, 45 Y, and 22 R), precluding the clear annotation of several genes. However, alignment against the mitochondrial genome of *Vipera berus* (NC_036956, total length 16,370 bp) shows that our new sequence has the typical mitochondrial structure of 13 protein-coding genes, 22 tRNA genes (although *tRNA-Thr* has not been recovered), two rRNA genes, and two control regions.

The results of our phylogenetic analyses are in agreement with those of previously

published Viperinae molecular studies using mitochondrial and nuclear data (Figs 3, S3, S5 and S6). We recapitulate with high support (i.e., Bayesian Posterior Probability [PP] = 1.0; Maximum Likelihood Bootstrap [MLB] > 95%) the monophyly of *Daboia*, *Macrovipera*, *Montivipera*, *Vipera*, and clades comprising *Daboia/Vipera* and *Macrovipera/Montivipera* (e.g., Garrigues *et al.*, 2005; Wüster *et al.*, 2008; Alencar *et al.*, 2016; Šmíd & Tolley, 2019). We also recover the expected relationships among the *Vipera aspis*, *V. berus*, and *V. ursinii* species groups within *Vipera*, as well as the basal position of *V. ammodytes* (e.g., Zinenko *et al.*, 2015; Alencar *et al.*, 2016; Šmíd & Tolley, 2019). Likewise, the relationships among the *Montivipera raddei* (Boettger, 1980) and *M. bornmuelleri* (Werner, 1898) species groups as well as the *M. xanthina* clade within *Montivipera* are consistent with the results of past studies (e.g., Alencar *et al.*, 2016; Stümpel *et al.*, 2016; Šmíd & Tolley, 2019), as are the relationships among the monophyletic clade comprising *Daboia mauritanica* (Gray, 1849)/*D. palaestinae* (Werner, 1938) and *D. siamensis* (Šmíd & Tolley, 2019). In our analyses of Dataset 1 (Figs. S3 and S6), *Vipera latastei* is the sister taxon of the snake fossil remains from Eivissa (PP = 1, MLB = 100), within the *V. aspis* species group. In our analyses of Dataset 2 (Figs. 3 and S5), which includes more representatives of *V. latastei/monticola*, the Eivissan viper falls within the variability of the East CNS (East Central-North-South clade, *sensu* Martínez-Freiría *et al.*, 2020, which is named the NE-SE-CN clade by Velo-Antón *et al.*, 2012) *V. latastei* populations (PP = 1.0, MLB = 100). This result raises the possibility that the extinct Eivissan viper should be considered an extinct insular population derived from Eastern Lataste's Viper.

Our calibrated trees (Figs. 3 and S6) also agree with divergence ages obtained for comparable nodes reported by other authors using diverse calibration points (e.g., Wüster *et al.*, 2008; Pook *et al.*, 2009; Velo-Antón *et al.*, 2012; Pyron & Burbrink, 2014; Alencar *et al.*, 2016; Zheng & Wiens, 2016; Šmíd & Tolley, 2019), except for Fenwick *et al.* (2012) who generally obtained younger ages for some nodes (Fig. S7). The split between the Eivissan viper sample and its nearest relative in Dataset 1 (*Vipera latastei*) was estimated at 2.67 Myr

(95% Highest Posterior Density, HPD = 1.83–3.55 Myr) (Fig. S6). However, the representative of *V. latastei* used in Dataset 1 was a combination of sequences from the western Iberian clades CW-S and CNW-SW (*sensu* Velo-Antón *et al.*, 2012; Accession numbers JX649564, KY762037, KY762066, MG875549) and from unknown origin within Spain (AY21074).

Our analyses of Dataset 2 suggest the Eivissan viper forms a clade with the East CNS samples (Figs. 3 and S5), which according to our data diverged 0.97 Mya (95% Highest Posterior Density, HPD = 0.67–1.31 Myr), in concordance with the < 1.5 Mya age calculated by Velo-Antón *et al.* (2012) and Martínez-Freiría *et al.* (2020). While our node age estimates within *V. latastei* could possibly be biased by violation of the Birth-Death tree prior in BEAST (which assumes samples belong to different species) and the time dependency of molecular rates (e.g., Subramanian & Lambert, 2011), we believe any effect of these biases is likely to be minimal because the *V. latastei* samples in Dataset 2 represent highly divergent populations (some representing subspecies level taxa) and our node ages are broadly consistent with previously published estimates. Within the East CNS clade, the split between the Eivissan viper and its sister taxon (*V. latastei* individual from the NE population) is 0.71 Myr (95% Highest Posterior Density, HPD = 0.41–1.01 Myr), but this node is poorly supported (PP = 0.68). Importantly, either estimate substantially postdates the last possible opportunity for colonization by means of a land bridge between the Balearic Islands and the Iberian Peninsula during the Messinian Salinity Crisis (MSC, 5.97–5.32 Myr; Krijgsman *et al.*, 1999; Manzi *et al.*, 2013).

We cannot establish a clear placement of the Eivissan viper within the East CNS *Vipera latastei* populations using Maximum Likelihood or Bayesian Inference phylogenetic analyses, however, the haplogroup network (Fig. 2) suggests that it should be considered as a separate population, being more genetically similar (> 98% similarity, Fig. S8) to the individuals from the North-East Iberian East-CNS population (i.e., from localities in

Tarragona, Castelló, Barcelona, Huesca and Lleida). The East-CNS population diverged from the East-South population about 2.66 Mya and diversified about 1.13 Mya (Velo-Antón *et al.*, 2012; Martínez-Freiría *et al.*, 2020).

TAXONOMIC STATUS OF THE EIVISSAN VIPER

Island Biology is a key discipline for evolutionary studies. The Theory of Evolution was born on islands and a lot of its stronger documentation comes from the islands. Species arriving to an isolated island after crossing a sea barrier start to evolve on the island from a first colonizer propagule, which initially does not differ from its mainland ancestors. Although the split from its ancestral mainland species (and its consequent reproductive isolation) can be established at the time of the arrival on the island, it is obvious that the colonizers are exactly the same as those of the population from which they come. From a morphological and genetic point of view both belong to the same species. The evolutionary adaptation to the new ecological conditions of the island (together with the ecological transformations of the insular ecosystems produced by the colonizers and their descendants) leads to the rise on the island of a new differentiated taxon through the speciation process. Within this process, two questions arise: How long does it take for a distinct new taxon to originate? What kind of differences are necessary for the derived population to be considered a different taxon?

The origin of a new species on islands can be exceptionally quick (e.g., Lamichhaney *et al.*, 2017, argue that speciation may occur over only a few generations through ‘hybrid speciation’), although it seems reasonable to expect that it usually takes longer. However, overall there are very few data on the minimum time necessary for the origin of a new species. Hume & Martill (2019) documented that *Dryolimnas cuvieri aldabranus* (Pucheran, 1845), the Aldabran flightless rail, evolved on Aldabra in less (perhaps much less) than 100,000 years. If we restrict the question to ophidians, we can estimate the age of new taxa

through geological and genetic data. For example, among the Galápagos islands, the youngest island inhabited by a snake is Fernandina (with the geological age of subaerial lava 0.1–0.03 Ma), where a differentiated subspecies of *Pseudalsophis occidentalis* (Van Denburgh, 1912) exists. It derives from *P. occidentalis* from Isabela (with the geological age for subaerial lava of 0.8–0.5 Ma). From these geological ages, the origin of the Fernandina subspecies should be no older than 100,000 years, and could be as young as 30,000 years. The presumed origin of the species *P. occidentalis* occurred as long as 800,000 years ago, but perhaps as recently as 500,000 years. In the Indian Ocean Comoros, an endemic subspecies of *Lycodrias cococola* Hawlitschek, Nagy & Glaw, 2012 arose on Grande Comoro, an island 10,000 years old. Together, these data suggest that a recognizable subspecies can arise in as little as tens of thousands of years, though the origin of a distinct species probably requires more time.

Although morphological differences between the Eivissan Viper and the Lataste's Viper could be large enough to probably consider them as different species, the genetic analysis confirms that it derives from the mainland *Vipera latastei*. Thus, as a conservative compromise, we present it here as a morphologically highly different subspecies of *V. latastei*.

SYSTEMATIC PALEONTOLOGY

SERPENTES LINNAEUS, 1758

VIPERIDAE OPPEL, 1811

VIPERA LAURENTI, 1768

VIPERA LATASTEI BOSCÁ, 1878

***VIPERA LATASTEI EBUSITANA* SUBSP. NOV.**

Etymology: *ebusitana* from Ebusus, the Latin adaptation of Ibosim, which was the Phoenician name for the island of Eivissa. We propose the common names “Eскурçó nan d’Eivissa”

(Catalan), “Víbora enana de Ibiza” (Spanish), and “Dwarf Eivissan Viper” (English).

Holotype: Complete middle trunk vertebra IMEDEA 106587 (Fig. 4).

Paratypes: cervical vertebrae (IMEDEA 106535, 106568, 106615, 106618, 106628, 106661, 106689, 106702, 106707, 106713, 106769, 106778), anterior trunk vertebrae (IMEDEA 106579, 106649, 106686, 106693, 106705, 106720, 106750, 106768), middle trunk vertebrae (IMEDEA 106544, 106558, 106564, 106567, 106619, 106629, 106637, 106646, 106652, 106660, 106685, 106691, 106748, 106766, 106777, 106779, 106789) and posterior trunk vertebrae (IMEDEA 106551, 106576, 106621, 106651, 106668, 106711, 106718), pterygoid fragment (IMEDEA 106589), compound bones (IMEDEA 106534, 106590, 106591, 106644, 106721, 106784, 106829, 106830, 106831, 106838).

Type locality and Horizon: Es Pouàs (Sant Antoni de Portmany, Eivissa, Pityusic Islands), grid square A2, level -110/-130 cm.

Chronology: At least Late Pleistocene–Holocene. A sample of 64 vertebrae (IMEDEA 106583) has been dated by at the C14 Laboratory of the Institut Royal du Patrimoine Artistique / Koninklijk Instituut voor het Kunstpatrimonium of Brussels (RICH-24981: 17,620–17,320 2 σ cal BC; Late Pleistocene).

Additional referred material: Es Pouàs (Sta. Agnès de Corona, Eivissa): 5,925 vertebrae numbered in groups from different levels (see Table 2).

Diagnosis: The following combination of diagnostic characters is exclusive of *Vipera latastei ebusitana* **subsp. nov.**: A Lataste’s Viper subspecies smaller than the extant Iberian populations of this species, with a body size similar to that of the *V. latastei/monticola* populations from the High Atlas, the cotyle, and especially the condyle, of the trunk vertebrae are characteristically rounded; the diameter of the condyle is very similar to that of the neural canal and proportionally smaller than that of mainland populations of *V. latastei*. The diapophysis is prominent and subspherical. The subcentral ridge is poorly developed. In

dorsal view, the trilobular zygosphenes display a central lobule with the same height (or slightly higher) than the lateral ones. The predominantly acute prezygapophyseal processes are very short. The articular facets of the zygankrum are generally partially visible as two small tips in dorsal and ventral views. The pterygoid (essentially the anterior branch) is proportionally short and wide and possesses a compacted dentition. The compound bone has a vertical and rectilinear prearticular crest.

Measurements: Tables 3 and 4.

Description of the type material:

Vertebrae

Around 6,000 trunk and cervical vertebrae have been recovered from different stratigraphic levels of Es Pouàs, but for the description up to 45 specimens, including 33 trunk vertebrae and 12 cervical vertebrae, have been selected on the basis of best preservation conditions.

Cervical vertebrae

The cervical vertebrae display the following characteristics: the cotyle and the condyle are notably smaller than the neural canal (Fig. 4A, B), the neural spine is higher than long (Fig. 4C), the centrum length is shorter than that of the trunk vertebrae (Fig. 4C), the hypapophyses are straight, elongated and quite vertically oriented (Fig. 4C), and the prezygapophyseal processes are more reduced than those of the trunk vertebrae (Fig. 4D, E)

Trunk vertebrae

The trunk vertebrae analyzed are characterized by their small size, with a centrum length 2.29–3.19 mm in adult specimens ($n = 33$; $CL_{\text{mean}} = 2.74$ mm). In anterior view (Fig. 4F, K), the zygosphenes present a slight convex dorsal surface and are slightly wider than the cotyle. The prezygapophyseal facets are inclined upward. The cotyle is slightly wider than high, and the diameter is similar to that of the neural canal. On each side of the cotyle there is a shallow paracotylar depression with a well-developed paracotylar foramen. The

parapophyseal process is well developed, subtriangular, and with a blunt apex.

In posterior view (Fig. 4G, L), the neural arch is dorso-ventrally compressed. The zygantrum is deep and shows well-developed articular facets. The postzygapophysis is inclined upward. The condyle is subcircular and its diameter is slightly smaller than the diameter of the neural canal.

In lateral view (Fig. 4H, M), the neural spine is considerably longer than high. The anterior margin is vertical and higher than the posterior, and the latter is inclined backward. Just below the interzygapophyseal constriction margin (= interzygapophyseal ridge or *margo lateralis*) there is a small lateral foramen on a flat surface latero-ventrally inclined. The hypapophysis is directed postero-ventrally, exceeding the posterior margin of the condyle. The antero-ventral margin of the hypapophysis displays an open sigmoidal shape, while the postero-dorsal is practically rectilinear, especially in the anterior trunk vertebrae. The prezygapophyseal processes have a circular section. Diapophyses and parapophyses of similar size; the diapophyses are subspherical and more prominent than the parapophyses. These are oval with a diffuse contour and are distally extended by a ridge on the lateral edge of the parapophyseal process. The parapophyseal processes are anteroventrally projected and anteroposteriorly flattened.

In dorsal view (Fig. 4I, N), these vertebrae have a weak interzygapophyseal constriction. The anterior margin of the zygosphenes is trilobulate, the lateral lobes have a more acute profile and generally they display a similar degree of development (or slightly less developed) than the central one. The articular surfaces of the prezygapophysis have a subrhomboidal shape. The prezygapophyseal processes, which are very short (around 1/6 of the total length of the prezygapophyseal surfaces) and with a blunt or slightly sharp apex, are anterolaterally oriented. The neural spine is thin and it anteriorly reaches about half of the total length of the zygosphenes and posteriorly exceeds the neural arch. The back end of the articular facets of the zygantrum are sometimes visible and displayed as two small tips. The

posterior neural wings lack the epizygapophyseal spines. The posterior notch is shallow with a posterior angle which is between 90° (anterior trunk vertebra) and 120° (posterior trunk vertebra).

In ventral view (Fig. 4J, O), the centrum is longer than wide (centrum length/centrum width 1.3–1.5) and displays a subtriangular shape with a convex ventral surface and a diffuse subcentral ridge, especially in the posterior half of the vertebrae. The basis of the hypapophysis extends anteriorly as a haemal keel that becomes wider until it reaches the basis of the cotyle. On each side of the haemal keel there is a small subcentral foramen. The parapophyseal processes are well developed, subrectangular with a round anterior limit. A narrow and well-marked groove separates them from the cotyle. The diapophysis presents a globular shape and the paraphophysis is reduced and it is closely placed to the latero-ventral margin of the parapophyseal process. The postzygapophyseal facets display an ovoid to subrectangular shape and are well developed. The condyle presents a well-defined precondylar constriction.

Pterygoid

IMEDEA 106589 is an anterior fragment of a right pterygoid that measures 3.52 mm from the anterior branch (or palatal process) to the anterior limit of the ectopterygoid process, and 0.44 mm width in the middle point (Fig. 5). The anterior end (= insertion area with the palatine) is bilobed with anterolateral and anteromedial processes, the first slightly more developed. Its anterior region is compressed lateromedially, then it is flattened in lateral view from the ectopterygoid process to the posterior region. Posteriorly, and in dorsal view, the impression of the posterior branch of the ectopterygoid is visible on the ectopterygoid process. The ectopterygoid process is well developed, starting at the pterygoid flange and becoming wider backwards. In ventral view, the ectopterygoid process is placed between the 7th and the 8th teeth position, displaying a set of teeth very close to each other with a ratio Number of teeth/Length from the anterior tip to the ectopterygoid process ($7/3.52$) = 1.99.

Compound bones

Ten fragmented compound bones have been recovered from Es Pouàs, and only IMEDEA 106831 is a near-complete specimen (Fig. 6). All of them display the typical viperid pattern, i.e., mandibles characterized by long compound bones strongly curved with well prominent prearticular crests and very low surangular crest (ratio between maximum height of the prearticular crest and surangular crest between 3 and 4). The near-complete specimen IMEDEA 106831 has a maximum length of 9.80 mm (estimated total mandibular – i.e., compound bone + dentary – ~ 13.4 mm), and its prearticular crest has a maximum height of 1.80 mm, whereas this measure is 1.86 mm in IMEDEA 106721. The prearticular crest is vertical and, in dorsal view, quite rectilinear; the mandibular fossa is narrow and deep. The retroarticular process is well developed, slightly longer than the glenoid fossa, it is medially curved, and with a blunt end. In lateral view, the mental foramen has an elliptical shape and it is open frontwards. In medial view, the infraglenoidal groove is well developed.

BODY SIZE ESTIMATION

Our estimation of the body size of the Eivissan Viper using the most complete vertebrae – including the largest available vertebrae – indicates an adult average total length of 36 cm (29–44 cm, n = 18). Following Boback (2003), we used the comparison between the maximum total lengths to establish unequivocally the condition of dwarfism of the Eivissan Viper in comparison to the Iberian populations from which it derives. We compared these measurements with the data for *Vipera latastei* European populations obtained in the literature (maximum total length above 70 cm; Brito *et al.*, 2006, Martínez-Freiría *et al.*, 2014), especially in the Iberian origin populations of *V. l. ebusitana* (maximum total length 71.9 cm; Brito *et al.*, 2006).

DIFFERENCES BETWEEN MAINLAND *V. LATASTEI* AND *V. L. EBUSITANA* SUBSP.

NOV.

Vipera latastei ebusitana differs morphologically from the Iberian *V. latastei* in the following traits: the trunk vertebrae of the fossil present a smaller and more rounded cotyle and condyle (Fig. 4F, G, K, L). The latter has a diameter similar or slightly smaller than the neural canal (Fig. 4G, L). In mainland *V. latastei* the cotyle and the condyle are subelliptical and the condyle has a larger diameter than that of the neural canal (Fig. 4U, V). Anterior and posterior parts of the neural arch have a similar height in *V. l. ebusitana*, (Fig. 4H) whereas in mainland *V. latastei* it is higher posteriorly (Fig. 4W). The diapophyses of *V. l. ebusitana* are well developed and present a subspherical shape whereas the parapophyses are indistinct from the parapophyseal process (Fig. 4H, M). In mainland *V. latastei* the diapophyses are elongated dorso-ventrally and the parapophyses have a diffuse outline but are well defined (Fig. 4W). The subcentral ridge is poorly developed in *V. l. ebusitana* (Fig. 4H, M), whereas in mainland *V. latastei* it is very well marked (Fig. 4W). The zygosphene is trilobulate in both taxa, but in *V. l. ebusitana*, the central lobule is similar or slightly longer than the lateral ones (Fig. 4D, I), whereas in mainland *V. latastei* the lateral lobules are more developed than the central one (Fig. 4X). Similarly, *V. l. ebusitana* and mainland *V. latastei* have short prezygapophyseal processes, but in the first one these processes are generally more acute than in the second (Fig. 4I, N, X). In *V. l. ebusitana* the articular facets of the zygantrum are extended posteriorly forming two small spines visible in the dorsal/ventral view of the vertebra (Fig. 4N), whereas in mainland *V. latastei* the zygantrum remains completely covered (hidden) by the neural arch (Fig. 4X). On the other hand, the anterior branch of the pterygoid of *V. l. ebusitana* is proportionally shorter and wider than in mainland *V. latastei* (Length/Width = 7.1 mm/0.81 mm). Moreover, *V. l. ebusitana* presents a ratio teeth number/ length ($7/3.52 = 1.99$) higher than in mainland *V. latastei* (ectopterygoid process located between the 8th and 9th tooth; $8/7.10 = 1.13$). The compound bone displays a vertical and, in dorsal view, a rectilinear prearticular crest in *V. l. ebusitana* (Fig. 6C), whereas in mainland *V. latastei* this prearticular

crest is slightly medially inclined and curved medially in dorsal view (Fig. 6F).

THE CAUDAL VERTEBRA FROM COVA DE CA NA REIA

The posterior caudal vertebra IMEDEA 106848 from Cova de ca na Reia is in poor preservation conditions. Just a good portion of the neural crest, a part of the left prezygapophysis, a small portion of the postzygapophyses and the base of the neural spine is preserved, while the anterior margin of the zygosphene is eroded. The cotyle, the condyle and the pleurapophyses also are totally eroded.

The total ventral length of this fragmented vertebra is 1.92 mm. In anterior view, the dorsal surface of the zygosphene is convex (Fig. 4P). The neural arch is moderately flattened in posterior view (Fig. 4P, Q). The neural spine is considerably thick (Fig. 4P, Q, S) and longer than high (Fig. 4R). The hemapophyses are clearly individualized in the posterior half of the centrum and converging anteriorly (Fig. 4T). Despite the hemapophyses are incomplete the left one is clearly incurved, i.e., the concavity is on the inner side.

DISCUSSION

COLONIZATION OF EIVISSA

The chronological and stratigraphical data from Es Pouàs confirm the presence of the Dwarf Eivissan Viper (*Vipera latastei ebusitana*) over at least c. 30,000 years, which combined with its distinctive morphological and genetic characteristics suggest that it should be considered a new taxon resulting from rapid evolutionary process under insular conditions. The genetic approach presented here suggests that the Dwarf Eivissan Viper diverged from the East CNS mainland *V. latastei* about 1 Mya (East CNS crown age: mean = 0.97 Myr; 95% Highest Posterior Density, HPD = 0.67–1.31 Myr), consistent with the East CNS clade node ages estimated by other authors (i.e., < 1.5 Myr; Velo-Antón *et al.*, 2012; Martínez-Freiría *et al.*, 2020). Thus, our data allow us to conclude that the ancestors of the Dwarf Eivissan Viper

arrived in Eivissa between 1.31 Myr (upper bound of the East CNS crown age 95% HPD) and c. 30,000 (first appearance of this taxon in the fossil record). This conservative date range suggests colonization of the island was via an overseas dispersal event, as the last land connection between Iberia and the Balearic Islands occurred 5.6–5.33 Mya (e.g., Mas *et al.*, 2018). Such overseas colonization is widely reported for reptiles arriving to offshore islands, such as the Canary Islands (e.g., *Gallotia* Boulenger, 1916, Cox *et al.*, 2010; or a boid snake on Lanzarote, Barahona *et al.*, 1998) and the Galápagos Islands [e.g., *Pseudalsophis*, Zaher *et al.*, 2009 (Zaher *et al.*, 2018)]. The current distance between Eivissa and Iberia is only about 90 km, which reduced to c. 70 km during Pleistocene glacial periods, and so could plausibly have been overcome by rafting on flotsam (as demonstrated by the dispersal of snakes to isolated islands like Galápagos, among others).

The poor preservation condition of the caudal vertebra from the deposit Cova de ca na Reia precludes its accurate taxonomic identification. Consequently, its attribution to *Vipera* is only tentative, and we designate it as cf. *Vipera* on the basis of the curvature of the hemapophyses. Direct comparison between available caudal vertebrae of different Colubridae [*Hemorrhoids hippocrepis* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Zamenis scalaris* (Schinz, 1822) and *Macroprotodon mauritanicus* Guichenot, 1850] and of different species of *Vipera* has allowed us to verify that the hemapophyses in *Vipera* are medially arched, as observed in the Cova de ca na Reia specimen, whereas in the different species of Colubridae s.l. the hemapophyses are vertically oriented. All points indicate that it represents the ancestor of the Es Pouàs viper, although this needs further confirmation. If the vertebra from the Cova de ca na Reia site actually belongs to the ancestor of the new subspecies described here (i.e., *Vipera latastei ebusitana*), its presence in this site (in combination with our molecular dating results) would restrict the age of this deposit to the Calabrian, whereas it was previously tentatively attributed to the Gelasian/Calabrian on the base of its malacological fauna.

EXTINCTION CHRONOLOGY AND CAUSES

Fossils of the *V. l. ebusitana* have been retrieved over a wide range of pre-human levels in Es Pouàs deposit (at least between 5295 and 32,523 BC), while it is apparently absent at levels postdating the first evidence of human presence (i.e., postdating 2139 BC; Alcover, 2008). The extinction of the species presumably occurred between 2139 and 5295 BC. The sole notable event occurring on Eivissa during this time period was the human arrival. Climate-related causes of the extinction of the Eivissan Viper can be excluded as no remarkable climatic changes occurred during this interval, leaving therefore only human-driven impacts as potential causes of its disappearance.

The impact of first human settlers on the Eivissan ecosystems could derive from three main causes (or their combined effect), which are known to affect populations of snakes everywhere: (1) transformation/depauperation of ecosystems (e.g., Henderson & Powell, 1996; Bailon *et al.*, 2015; Bochaton *et al.*, 2015, 2019); (2) direct hunting of the species (e.g. Tóth *et al.*, 2010); and (3) introduction of alien species (e.g., Steadman, 1986; Henderson, 1992; Powell, 1999, 2002).

Although all these human activities could have potentially contributed to the extinction process, the first two impacts should have only had a limited effect on the viper's extinction due to the size and rocky landscape of the island. . Thus, excluding these potential causes for extinction, the introduction by humans of alien species emerges as the most plausible cause for the Eivissan Viper extinction.

First human settlers introduced several mammals, but there is no record of introduction of reptiles over all the Eivissan Prehistory, which precludes the introduction of specific reptile diseases as a possible cause for the Dwarf Eivissan Viper extinction. The first introduced mammals exclusively consist of five domesticated taxa (cow, sheep, goat, pig, and dog), and two wild rodents (Wood Mouse and Garden Mouse). (Alcover, 2008). Among these introduced mammals, just dogs, pigs, and rodents should be considered as potential snake

predators. Dogs presumably arrived with the first settlers to Eivissa, but there is no evidence that they ever became feral. Although dogs can potentially kill snakes, the dog population density should have been high enough to have a noticeable effect on the viper's population, and there is no record of it (Valenzuela, 2015). The same applies to *Sus scrofa*: although they are potential consumers of vipers (e.g., Maritz *et al.*, 2016), the density of feral pigs required to produce the viper's extinction should have been high, which is not supported by the archaeological record.

Thus, only the two rodents could be considered as potential causes of the extinction of the Dwarf Eivissan Viper. Without mammal predators, the increase of populations of both rodents should have been explosive after their arrival, as occurs invariably with invasive rodents on territories without mammals (e.g., Hardouin *et al.*, 2010; Nathan *et al.*, 2015). Both species include animal items in their diet. However, the Wood Mouse can be reasonably excluded as a potential predator of the Dwarf Eivissan Viper, as it only occasionally predaes on small invertebrates while no records of predation on small vertebrates exist (e.g., Hansson, 1985).

Eliomys quercinus (Linnaeus, 1758) emerges as the potential agent causing the extinction of the Dwarf Eivissan Viper. In contrast with the Wood Mouse, it is well documented that the Garden Dormouse depredates on small vertebrates, including lizards and small mammals (e.g., Kahmann & Lau, 1972). It also has high resistance to viper venom (Phisalix, 1930, 1931; Storch, 1978). Rodents are considered prolific invasive species (e.g., Atkinson, 1985; Drake & Hunt, 2009), especially in the absence of predatory mammals, and founder populations on an island would have quickly increased (e.g., Hardouin *et al.*, 2010; Nathan *et al.*, 2015). The high adaptability of *E. quercinus* to all the range of habitats of Eivissa could have also contributed to the rapid increase of its populations. In addition, vipers are viviparous and they produce a reduced number of small-sized young, which should have been an easily available resource for the Garden Dormouse.

Alien rodents introduced into the Balearics by humans have been considered as key elements in the transformation of pristine ecosystems (Traveset *et al.*, 2009). Here we propose that the introduction of the Garden Dormouse could have played a pivotal role in the extinction of the Dwarf Eivissan Viper, although the effect of other human-caused environmental alterations may have played a role in the decline of this species.

BODY SIZE EVOLUTION

The dwarfism of the Eivissan viper (with an adult total length estimated at 36 cm [29–44 cm, n = 18]) is most probably related to the influence of island selective forces such as the size of available prey. The diet of adult specimens of *V. latastei* in the Iberian Peninsula is based mainly on small mammals, and on lizards for juvenile vipers (Martínez-Freiría *et al.*, 2014). In a similar way to dwarf *Vipera latastei-monticola* from the High Atlas (see Saint-Girons, 1980; Freitas *et al.*, 2018) and *Vipera aspis* from the Montecristo island (Luiselli *et al.*, 2015), geographic isolation and a diet of adults likely restricted to lizards could have led to dwarfism in the Eivissan viper. For comparison, total size estimates using 31 adults of *V. latastei-monticola* from the West and Central regions of High Atlas yielded ranges between 33.5 cm (standard deviation 5.13) for male individuals and 32.1 cm (standard deviation 2.09) for female individuals (F. Martínez-Freiría, unpublished data).

The evolution of body size in insular snakes has been analyzed by many different authors. Case (1978) found a general trend – with a few exceptions – towards dwarfism of snakes on islands, whereas Boback (2003) and Boback & Guyer (2003) described an evolutionary trend towards gigantism in colubrids and towards dwarfism in viperids, the latter recorded in extant individuals of nine species of *Crotalus* Linnaeus, 1758, one species of *Bothrops* Wagler, 1824, and two species of *Vipera*. No examples of evolution towards dwarfism had been recorded among fossil viper species so far, and thus the case presented here is the first palaeontological evidence supporting the evolutionary trend towards dwarfism

in island viperids postulated by Boback (2003) and Boback & Guyer (2003).

CONCLUSION

Traditionally, three morphological complexes are identified within the species formerly included in the genus *Vipera* (Szyndlar, 1991): the “Oriental Vipers Complex” (OVC), including the largest species currently in genera *Macrovipera*, *Montivipera*, and *Daboia*; the “*aspis* complex”, including *V. ammodytes*, *V. latastei*, *V. aspis* and others; and the “*berus* complex”, including smaller members of the genus as *V. berus*, *V. ursinii*, and others. Typically, vertebrae of the “*berus* complex” can be defined as small, elongate, and characterised by low neural spines and hypapophyses whereas those of the “OVC” are large, relatively short, and have high spines and hypapophyses. Vertebrae of the “*aspis* complex” (in which *V. latastei* is included) display intermediate conditions between the “*berus* complex” and the “OVC”. Although morphological differences in skeletal remains among these complexes should be clear, the morphology within each complex is highly homogeneous. In addition, differences in the vertebral morphology between the extant species of the “*berus*” and “*aspis*” complexes could be related to body size. Thus, the proper identification of isolated vertebrae, and the resolution of phylogenetic relationships from a morphological approach is usually very difficult. The distinctive morphology and size of the fossil viper remains from Eivissa described in this paper could have been potentially enough to describe a new species belonging to *Vipera* within the “*aspis* complex”. However, DNA sequences have instead allowed its attribution to a new subspecies of *V. latastei*, the identification of the mainland origin population, and thus the establishment of an insular evolutionary scenario for the phenotypic differences observed in the vertebrae recovered from the deposit of Es Pouàs.

For these reasons, whenever possible, the combination of morphological and ancient DNA approaches proposed here is important for properly establishing the appropriate taxonomic and phylogenetic attribution of fossil viper vertebrae.

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FIGURE CAPTIONS

Figure 1. Geographical context of the Pityusic Islands and location of the paleontological sites of Es Pouàs and Cova de Ca na Reia in Eivissa (Balearic Islands, Western Mediterranean).

Figure 2. Haplogroup network analysis of 76 *Vipera latastei/monticola* individuals and the *V. latastei ebusitana* (15951, in black) sequences (270 bp *CYTB* + 602 bp *ND4*). A, Network estimated using Fitchi algorithm. B, Geographical location of individuals including identification numbers for those sequences more similar to *V. latastei ebusitana* according to network analysis. See Table S4 for details about geographical origin of samples and accession numbers.

Figure 3. Phylogenetic position of *Vipera latastei ebusitana* (sample 19591) within Viperinae based on mitochondrial sequences (4,164 bp) and using BEAST. Nodes are labeled with Bayesian posterior probabilities (PP), and circles in nodes indicate PP = 1. Green bars represent 95% highest posterior density (HPD) intervals. Messinian Salinity Crisis (MSC) is indicated by blue shading. See Table S2 for information about individual samples and accession numbers. Time in million years before present (BP).

Figure 4. Vertebrae from Eivissan extinct snakes and extant mainland *Vipera latastei*. A–E, cervical vertebra (IMEDEA 106535), F–J, anterior trunk vertebra (IMEDEA 106693), and K–O, middle trunk vertebra (holotype, IMEDEA 106587) from *Vipera latastei ebusitana*. P–T, caudal vertebra (IMEDEA 106848) attributed to cf. *Vipera*. U–Y, middle trunk vertebra (IMEDEA 106925) from mainland *Vipera latastei*. Anterior views (A, F, K, P, U), posterior views (B, G, L, Q, V), lateral views (C, H, M, R, W), dorsal views (D, I, N, S, X) and ventral

views (E, J, O, T, Y). Scale bar: 3 mm.

Figure 5. *Vipera latastei* pterygoids. A–B, *Vipera latastei ebusitana* (IMEDEA 106589) from Es Pouàs. C–D, mainland *Vipera latastei* (MNHN-ZA-AC 2020-1). Ventral views (A, C) and dorsal views (B, D). Scale bar: 5 mm.

Figure 6. *Vipera latastei* compound bones. A–C, *Vipera latastei ebusitana* (IMEDEA 106831) from Es Pouàs. D–F, mainland *Vipera latastei* (MNHN-ZA-AC 2020-1). Lateral views (A, D), medial views (B, E) and dorsal views (C, F). Scale bar: 5 mm.

TABLES

Table 1. Fossil record of Viperinae in the Mediterranean Islands.

Taxon	Locality	Site age	Reference
<i>V. latastei</i> subsp. nov.	Es Pouàs (Eivissa)	Late Pleistocene to Holocene	This paper
cf. <i>Vipera</i> sp.	Cova de ca na Reia (Eivissa)	Calabrian	This paper
<i>Vipera</i> sp. ('OVC')	Caló den Rafelino (Mallorca)	Pliocene	Bailon <i>et al.</i> , 2010
cf. <i>Vipera natiensis</i>	Caló den Rafelino (Mallorca)	Pliocene	Bover <i>et al.</i> , 2014
<i>Vipera</i> sp. ('OVC')	Na Burguesa-1 (Mallorca)	Zanclean	Torres <i>et al.</i> , 2014
<i>Vipera natiensis</i>	Punta Nati 12 (Menorca)	Pliocene	Bailon <i>et al.</i> , 2002
<i>Vipera</i> sp.	Punta Nati 3 and 12 (Menorca)	Probably Pliocene	Bailon <i>et al.</i> , 2002
Viperidae indet.	Punta Nati 2 (Menorca)	Middle Miocene	Bailon <i>et al.</i> , 2002
<i>Vipera</i> sp.	Monte Tuttavista (Sardinia)	Late Pliocene–Early Pleistocene	Abbazzi <i>et al.</i> , 2004
cf. <i>Vipera</i> , <i>Vipera</i> sp.	Capo Mannu D1 (Sardinia)	Late Pliocene	Pecorini <i>et al.</i> , 1974 ; Delfino <i>et al.</i> , 2011
<i>Vipera</i> sp. (' <i>aspis</i> ' group)	Oschiri (Sardinia)	Early Miocene	Venczel & Sanchíz, 2006
<i>Vipera</i> sp. (' <i>berus</i> ' group)	Laghada B (Kos Island)	Pleistocene	Szyndlar, 1991
Viperidae indet. ('OVC')	Chios Island	Middle Pleistocene	Schneider, 1975; Szyndlar, 1991
<i>Macrovipera lebetina</i>	Akrotiri Aetokremnos (Cyprus)	Holocene	Bailon, 1999
Viperidae indet.('OVC')	Gargano paleoisland	Late Miocene–Early Pliocene	Delfino, 2002

Table 2. Distribution of the 6,018 remains of *Vipera latastei ebusitana* at Es Pouàs. All numbers from the IMEDEA collection.

Grid	Level (cm)	IMEDEA Number	Bones
	Surface	106559–106576	29 vertebrae
	-70/-90	106840	1 vertebra
	-110/-130 (near wall)	106841	2 vertebrae
	-110/-130	106583-106587	116 vertebrae ⁽¹⁾
	-110/130 (wall)	106841	2 vertebrae
	-130/-150	106588–106610	688 vertebrae, 2 compound bones, 1 pterygoid
	-150/-170	106611–106616	549 vertebrae
	-170/-190	106617–106683	1.381 vertebrae ⁽²⁾ , 1 compound bone
A2	-190/-210	106684–106711	918 vertebrae
	-210/-230	106712–106721	132 vertebrae, 1 compound bone
	-230/-250	106722–106731	161 vertebrae
	-250/-270	106839	5 vertebrae
	-270/-290	106732–106784	1.026 vertebrae, 1 compound bone
	-290/-310	106785–106802	94 vertebrae
	-330/-350	106803–106832	228 vertebrae, 3 compound bones
	-350/-370	106833–106838	8 vertebrae, 1 compound bone
	Lower N3 (near wall)	106842	1 vertebrae
	Lower N3	106843	1 vertebra
	Lower N4	106844	6 vertebrae
	N6 (Near wall)	106554, 106556–106558	14 vertebrae
	Upper N6	106845	41 vertebrae
	Interfase N6-N7	106553, 106555	36 vertebrae ⁽²⁾
A3	N7 (near cave wall)	106542–106551	148 vertebrae ⁽²⁾
	N7 (far cave wall)	106541	152 vertebrae ⁽²⁾
	Upper N7 (far wall)	106533-106540	181 vertebrae, 1 compound bone
	Lower N7 (near wall)	106552	32 vertebrae
	Lower N7 (far wall)	106846	2 vertebrae
	N8A (far wall)	106847	3 vertebrae
A4	-220/-240	106579–106582	50 vertebrae
A5	-100/-120	106577, 106578	28 vertebrae

⁽¹⁾ From this level, 30 vertebrae were used for DNA analysis and 64 for radiocarbon dating. ⁽²⁾ Some of the vertebrae from this level were charred.

Table 3. Measurements (in mm) and indices of the intermediate trunk vertebrae of *Vipera latastei ebusitana*. Abbreviations: CL, Centrum length. CTH, Cotyle height. CTW, Cotyle width. GH, Greatest height of the vertebra. LNS, Length of the neural spine. MLV: Maximum length of the vertebra. MW, Maximum width. PO-PO, Width between the outer edges of postzygapophyseal articular surfaces. PR-PR, Width between the outer edges of prezygapophyseal articular surfaces. WIC, Width of the interzygapophyseal constriction. ZW, Zygosphene width.

Trunk vertebrae	n	Min	Mean	Max	SD
Measurements					
CL	18	2.29	2.74	3.19	0.27
CTH	18	0.85	1.00	1.13	0.09
CTW	18	1.07	1.22	1.33	0.08
GH	15	3.58	4.15	5.50	0.57
LNS	7	1.61	1.92	2.27	0.23
MLV	18	2.85	3.34	3.95	0.37
MW	17	3.30	3.92	4.72	0.47
PO-PO	15	2.97	3.50	4.30	0.45
PR-PR	18	2.97	3.62	4.39	0.46
WIC	18	1.63	1.96	2.40	0.24
ZW	16	1.48	1.74	1.98	0.15
Indices					
CL/WIC	18	1.24	1.40	1.55	0.08
CL/ZW	16	1.44	1.56	1.69	0.08
CTW/CTH	18	1.14	1.23	1.35	0.06
CTW/WIC	18	0.54	0.63	0.73	0.05
PO-PO/WIC	15	1.65	1.80	1.90	0.07
PR-PR/MLV	18	1.02	1.08	1.14	0.03
PR-PR/WIC	18	1.67	1.84	1.94	0.06
ZW/WIC	16	0.80	0.90	0.98	0.05

Table 4. Measurements (in mm) and indices of the cervical vertebrae of *Vipera latastei ebusitana*. Abbreviations: CL, Centrum length. CTH, Cotyle height. CTW, Cotyle width. GH, Greatest height of the vertebra. LNS, Length of the neural spine. MLV, Maximum length of the vertebra. MW, Maximum width. PO-PO, Width between the outer edges of postzygapophyseal articular surfaces. PR-PR, Width between the outer edges of prezygapophyseal articular surfaces. WIC, Width of the interzygapophyseal constriction. ZW, Zygosphene width.

Cervical vertebrae	n	Min	Mean	Max	SD
Measurements					
CL	11	2.10	2.45	3.03	0.25
CTH	11	0.77	0.92	1.03	0.08
CTW	11	0.95	1.08	1.29	0.11
GH	11	3.89	4.62	5.63	0.52
LNS	6	1.32	1.62	1.75	0.16
MLV	11	2.43	2.92	3.69	0.35
MW	11	2.62	3.47	4.41	0.46
PO-PO	9	2.67	3.23	4.12	0.47
PR-PR	11	2.60	3.26	4.19	0.44
WIC	10	1.48	1.77	2.23	0.22
ZW	11	1.40	1.61	1.98	0.17
Indices					
CL/WIC	10	1.30	1.39	1.44	0.04
CL/ZW	11	1.42	1.52	1.63	0.07
CTW/CTH	11	1.05	1.17	1.28	0.06
CTW/WIC	10	0.56	0.61	0.68	0.03
PO-PO/WIC	9	1.75	1.881	1.93	0.07
PR-PR/MLV	11	1.05	1.11	1.17	0.03
PR-PR/WIC	10	1.74	1.83	1.96	0.08
ZW/WIC	10	0.85	0.91	0.97	0.04

SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE CAPTIONS

Figure S1. Graphic illustrating the different steps in the Multi-reference Iterative Mapping Approach (MIMA) for the obtaining of the partial mitochondrial genome sequence for *Vipera latastei ebusitana*.

Figure S2. Results of mapDamage analyses of unique reads from *Vipera latastei ebusitana* in the Multi-reference Iterative Mapping Approach (MIMA). Substitution (4 top panels) and misincorporation (2 bottom panels) panels display the pattern typically observed in ancient samples.

Figure S3. A (left), Maximum-Likelihood and B (right), Bayesian phylogenetic relationships of Viperinae genera *Vipera*, *Montivipera*, *Macrovipera*, and *Daboia* available in GenBank using Dataset 1, including *Vipera latastei ebusitana* (sample 19591). The analysis was performed in RAxML and MrBayes using 4,164 bp of several mitochondrial genes (see Table S2 for accession number details and Table S3 for partitioning scheme). Bootstrap values for ML (MLB) and Bayesian Posterior Probabilities (PP) are given in each node. Nodes with circles indicate MLB = 100 and PP = 1, and nodes without value indicate MLB < 75 and PP < 0.95.

Figure S4. Maximum Likelihood (ML) tree of 76 *Vipera latastei/monticola* individuals and the *V. latastei ebusitana* (15951, in black) sequences (270 bp *CYTB* + 602 bp *ND4*) used to build haplogroup network of Figure 2. Circles in nodes of ML tree indicate Bootstrap values (MLB) = 100, whereas nodes without values MLB < 75. See Table S4 for details about geographical origin of samples and accession numbers. Haplogroup names following Freitas *et al.* (2018) for African populations and Martínez-Freiría *et al.*

(2020) for Iberian populations (CNW-SW and CW-S sub-groups within West populations following Velo-Antón *et al.*, 2012).

Figure S5. A (left), Maximum-Likelihood and B (right), Bayesian phylogenetic relationships of Viperinae genera *Vipera*, *Montivipera*, *Macrovipera*, and *Daboia* available in GenBank using Dataset 2, including *Vipera latastei ebusitana* (sample 19591) and individuals of *V. latastei* from different populations. The analysis was performed in RAxML and MrBayes using the same gene sequences as Dataset 1 genes (see Table S2 for accession number details and Table S3 for partitioning scheme). Bootstrap values for ML (MLB) and Bayesian posterior probabilities (PP) are given in each node. Nodes with circles indicate MLB = 100 and PP = 1, whereas nodes with no data indicate MLB < 75 and PP < 0.95. *V. latastei* individuals from West (W), South (STH), East-South (SOU), and East CNS (SE, CN, NE) populations.

Figure S6. Phylogenetic position of *Vipera latastei ebusitana* (sample 19591) within Viperinae based on mitochondrial sequences (4,164 bp) and using BEAST and Dataset 1. Nodes are labeled with Bayesian posterior probabilities (PP), and circles in nodes indicate PP = 1. Green bars represent 95% highest posterior density (HPD) intervals. Messinian Salinity Crisis (MSC) is indicated by blue shading. See Table S2 for information about individual samples and accession numbers. Time in million years before present (BP).

Figure S7. Comparison of split-ages for the different nodes in trees estimated in this paper and previous analyses published elsewhere (see references in the figure).

Figure S8. Heatmap of pairwise similarity between the *Vipera latastei ebusitana* and *V.*

latastei/monticola *CYTb* (270 bp) and *ND4* (602 bp) sequences from Velo-Antón *et al.* (2012), Martínez-Freiría *et al.* (2015, 2020), and Freitas *et al.* (2018). See Table S4 for accession numbers of the sequences used. Sequences for the extinct taxon are more similar (> 98% similarity) to the *V. latastei* ones from North-East Iberian East-CNS populations (*sensu* Martínez-Freiría *et al.*, 2020; or NE populations of NE-SE-CN clade *sensu* Velo-Antón *et al.*, 2012). Haplogroup names following Freitas *et al.* (2018) for African populations and Martínez-Freiría *et al.* (2020) for Iberian populations (CNW-SW and CW-S sub-groups within West populations following Velo-Antón *et al.*, 2012).

SUPPLEMENTARY TABLE CAPTIONS

Table S1. Measurements (in mm) of trunk vertebrae and indices of selected *Vipera* species and lineal regression used to estimate Total Body Length (TBL) of *Vipera latastei ebusitana* (see Table 3 for same measurements in *V. l. ebusitana*).

Abbreviations: CL, Centrum length. CTH, Cotyle height. CTW, Cotyle width. GH, Greatest height of the vertebra. LNS, Length of the neural spine. MLV, Maximum length of the vertebra. MW, Maximum width. PO-PO, Width between the outer edges of postzygapophyseal articular surfaces. PR-PR, Width between the outer edges of prezygapophyseal articular surfaces. TBL, Total body length. WIC, Width of the interzygapophyseal constriction. ZW, Zygosphene width.

Table S2. GenBank accession numbers of the different Viperinae sequences used for phylogenetic inference in Datasets 1 and 2.

Table S3. Optimal partitioning scheme inferred with PartitionFinder for a total alignment of 4,164 bp (213 bp for *12S_rRNA*, 327 bp for *16S_rRNA*, 840 bp for *COXI*, 1104 bp for *CYTB*, 1002 bp for *ND2*, and 678 bp for *ND4*) of 34 Viperinae species for Datasets 1 and 2. See Table S2 for accession number details. Partitioning scheme inferred selecting models implemented in each software (RAxML, MrBayes and BEAST).

Table S4. GenBank accession numbers and details of the different *Vipera latastei/monticola* *CYTB* (270 bp) and *ND4* (602 bp) sequences used for the haplotype network analysis. Clade names following (1) Velo-Antón *et al.* (2012), (2) Martínez-Freiría *et al.* (2020), and (3) Freitas *et al.* (2018).

SUPPLEMENTARY APPENDICES

Appendix S1. Dataset 1 alignment in PHYLIP format.

Appendix S2. Dataset 2 alignment in PHYLIP format.

Appendix S3. Alignment of *Vipera latastei/monticola* for haplogroup network analysis in PHYLIP format.

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Figure 1. Geographical context of the Pityusic Islands and location of the paleontological sites of Es Pouàs and Cova de Ca na Reia in Eivissa (Balearic Islands, Western Mediterranean).

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Figure 2. Haplogroup network analysis of 76 *Vipera latastei/monticola* individuals and the *V. latastei ebusitana* (15951, in black) sequences (270 bp CYTB + 602 bp ND4). A, Network estimated using Fitchi algorithm. B, Geographical location of individuals including identification numbers for those sequences more similar to *V. latastei ebusitana* according to network analysis. See Table S4 for details about geographical origin of samples and accession numbers.

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Figure 3. Phylogenetic position of *Vipera latastei ebusitana* (sample 19591) within Viperinae based on mitochondrial sequences (4,164 bp) and using BEAST. Nodes are labeled with Bayesian posterior probabilities (PP), and circles in nodes indicate PP = 1. Green bars represent 95% highest posterior density (HPD) intervals. Messinian Salinity Crisis (MSC) is indicated by blue shading. See Table S2 for information about individual samples and accession numbers. Time in million years before present (BP).

167x118mm (300 x 300 DPI)

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Figure 4. Vertebrae from Eivissan extinct snakes and extant mainland *Vipera latastei*. A–E, cervical vertebra (IMEDEA 106535), F–J, anterior trunk vertebra (IMEDEA 106693), and K–O, middle trunk vertebra (holotype, IMEDEA 106587) from *Vipera latastei ebusitana*. P–T, caudal vertebra (IMEDEA 106848) attributed to cf. *Vipera*. U–Y, middle trunk vertebra (IMEDEA 106925) from mainland *Vipera latastei*. Anterior views (A, F, K, P, U), posterior views (B, G, L, Q, V), lateral views (C, H, M, R, W), dorsal views (D, I, N, S, X) and ventral views (E, J, O, T, Y). Scale bar: 3 mm.

159x224mm (300 x 300 DPI)

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Figure 5. *Vipera latastei* pterygoids. A-B, *Vipera latastei ebusitana* (IMEDEA 106589) from Es Pouàs. C-D, mainland *Vipera latastei* (MNHN-ZA-AC 2020-1). Ventral views (A, C) and dorsal views (B, D). Scale bar: 5 mm.

180x184mm (300 x 300 DPI)

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Figure 6. *Vipera latastei* compound bones. A–C, *Vipera latastei ebusitana* (IMEDEA 106831) from Es Pouàs. D–F, mainland *Vipera latastei* (MNHN-ZA-AC 2020-1). Lateral views (A, D), medial views (B, E) and dorsal views (C, F). Scale bar: 5 mm.

180x49mm (300 x 300 DPI)